

late stages (207.0 kg N ha⁻¹, 65.3 kg P ha⁻¹, 124.5 kg K ha⁻¹) combined with increased foliar spray.

We studied genetic correlation and heritability for a trait defined as a ratio of two kernel-leaf characters in eight high-yielding rice cultivars. A randomized block design with three replications in 10.0-m² plots of medium soil were laid out at Yuanmou (elevation 118.4 m) under high-yield ecology and conventional management in Yunnan during the 1994 season.

The heritability of each character, a ratio of two component traits, and their genetic correlation for the means of 12 traits, were calculated (see table). The results showed that kernel characters had higher heritability than leaf characters, especially grain length (8.5%), grain width (98.3%), and grain per width (99.7%). Because the >10°C cumulative temperature was 3993.7 °C and rainfall was 424.4 mm during the rice cropping season in Yuanmou, climatic conditions were advantageous to full expression of kernel character inheritance in indica rice. Heritability of >90% included grain length/grain width (99.7%), grain length/filled grain width / yield ha⁻¹ (98.5%), grain length / 1000-grain weight (98.1%), flag leaf width/ yield ha⁻¹ (97.2%), flag leaf length/yield ha⁻¹ (95.3%), grain length/ yield ha⁻¹ (93.8%), grain width/100-grain weight (93.7%), flag leaf length/ grain weight panicle⁻¹ (92.0%), and 1000-grain weight /yield ha⁻¹ (91.9%). The ratio of kernel-leaf characters showed high heritability, especially grain length/width under the high-yield ecology of Yunnan. Yield ha⁻¹ was positively and significantly correlated with filled grains panicle⁻¹ (r=0.918), grain weight plant⁻¹ (r=0.821), grain width (r=0.471), grain weight plant⁻¹ (r=0.422), and spikelets panicle⁻¹ (r=0.419). A high-yielding cultivar should have medium width and short flag leaf, short and round kernel, moderate 1000-grain weight, and increased kernel number and grain weight panicle⁻¹. ■

Heterosis: early prediction and relationship with reproductive phase

C. H. M. Vijayakumar, M. I. Ahmed, B. C. Viraktamath, and M. S. Ramesha, Hybrid Rice Laboratory, Directorate of Rice Research, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030, Andhra Pradesh, India

We studied the relationship between reproductive phase and heterosis and looked for traits affecting heterosis. In the 1994 wet season at the International Hybrid Rice Observational Nursery (IRHON), 24 hybrids and their respective restorers (one plant each) were dissected to identify the initiation of reproductive phase marked by the formation of a hairy structure. Similarly in the 1995 wet season, three to five plants each from 20 hybrids and their 20 restorers were dissected. At maturity grain yield m⁻² and observations on several yield components in five selected plants were recorded as well as

days to 50% flowering for each hybrid and restorer (Table 1). Reproductive phase initiation occurred early in hybrids. Restorer yield in parents was higher than maintainer yield in all hybrid combinations. We found a definite, positive relation between better parent (restorer) heterosis and reproductive phase duration. (Table 1). In the H>R group, reproductive phase duration of hybrids was extended with no change in growth duration (days to 50% flowering). In group H<R, days to 50% flowering of hybrids was early compared with restorers but was unaccompanied by a change in reproductive phase duration.

Table 2 compares yield and yield components of hybrids and restorers. The yield superiority of hybrids or restorers was positively related to plant height. The number of filled spikelets was always high in hybrids. Hybrids possessed higher values for most yield traits than restorers, except in group H<R of IR62829A-based hybrids. The

Table 1. Relationship between reproductive phase duration and heterosis. Andhra Pradesh, India. 1994-95.

Season	Hybrids (no.)	Particulars	Reproductive phase initiation	Days to 50% flowering	Difference	Grain yield (g m ⁻²)
1994 WS	15	H>R:Hybrid	79 ^a	107	28 ^a	641 ^a
		:Restorer	86	109	23	509
	9	H<R:Hybrid	82 ^a	106 ^a	24	474 ^a
		:Restorer	88	110	22	583
1995 WS	8	H>R:Hybrid	64 ^a	95	31 ^a	624 ^a
		:Restorer	68	94	25	491
	12	H<R:Hybrid	64 ^a	90 ^a	26	473 ^a
		:Restorer	69	96	27	569
IR58025A-based hybrids	5	H>R:Hybrid	64 ^a	96	32	644 ^a
		:Restorer	72	96	24	473
		:IR58025B	70	93	23	323
	8	:Hybrid	66 ^a	92 ^a	26	458 ^a
		H<R:Restorer	71	97	26	577
		:IR58025B	70	93	23	323
IR62829A-based hybrids	3	:Hybrid	63	92	29 ^a	591
		H>R:Restorer	63	89	26	520
		:IR62828B	62	87	25	435
	4	:Hybrid	59	86	27	503 ^a
		H<R:Restorer	65	93	28	552
		:IR62829B	62	87	25	435

^a P=0.05.

Table 2. Traits affecting yield heterosis. Andhra Pradesh, India. 1995 WS.

Particular		Plant height	Tiller number	Panicle number	Panicle length	Panicle weight	Filled spikelets	Sterile spikelets	100-grain weight
H>R	:Hybrid	107	9.88	9.00 ^a	26.38	3.89	139	36	2.76
	:Restorer	105	9.00	7.75	25.28	3.47	113	19	2.63
H<R	:Hybrid	99	9.75	8.28	26.02 ^a	3.50	134 ^a	31 ^a	2.51
	:Restorer	104	9.83	8.33	24.52	3.34	114	20	2.32
IR58025A- based hybrids	:Hybrid	111	9.40	9.00	27.13	3.88	144	39	2.88
	:Restorer	108	8.80	7.60	25.75	3.44	111	18	2.68
	:IR58025B	98	10.00	9.00	26.02	3.48	132	32	1.94
H<R	:Hybrid	101	8.88	7.63	26.74 ^a	3.79	142 ^a	31	2.61 ^a
	:Restorer	105	10.13	8.50	24.11	3.42	118	21	2.27
	:IR58025B	98	10.00	9.00	26.02	3.48	132	32	1.94
IR62829B- based hybrids	:Hybrid	99	10.67	9.00	25.11	3.90	129	29	2.55
	:Restorer	99	9.33	8.00	24.15	3.53	115	22	2.55
	:IR62829B	83	11.00	10.00	24.38	3.16	99	18	1.94
H<R	:Hybrid	96	11.50	10.50 ^a	24.57	2.91	118	31	2.31
	:Restorer	103	9.25	8.00	25.34	3.19	106	17	2.41
	:IR62829B	83	11.00	10.00	24.38	3.16	99	18	1.94

^aSignificant at the 5% level.

yield superiority of those restorers comes mainly from grain weight. Higher yield of hybrids or restorers was related positively to tiller number and panicle number. The grain yield of hybrids in the H<R group (except IR62829A- based hybrids) was affected by tiller number / panicle number; for all other traits, hybrids were superior.

We found reproductive phase initiation always early in hybrids. Hybrids yield better than parents when their days to 50% flowering is similar or later than their respective restorers. The study indicates that hybrids with better performance can be identified right in the testcross nursery by comparing their tiller number, plant height, and days to 50%, flowering with their respective restorers. ■

Breeding methods

Callus induction and plant regeneration from anther culture of six high-yielding indica/basmati crosses

S. Dhaliwal, A. S. Sindhu, R. Sandhu-Gill, B. Singh, G. S. Sindhu, and S. S. Rosal, Biotechnology Center, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana 141004, India

Anther culture of F₁ hybrids facilitates recovery of rare gene combinations in a small population of doubled haploids (DH). Two main problems limit exploitation of anther culture from indica rices: low frequencies of callusing from cultured anthers and green plant regeneration from calli.

We attempted anther culture from six crosses of high-yielding indica and basmati varieties (Table 1). Young panicles were collected from field-grown plants at the commencement of flowering from primary tillers, when the distance between flag leaf base and the auricle of the penultimate leaf was 4-7 cm. After cold pretreatment (4 °C) for 7-10 d, anthers with microspores at the early uninucleate stage were cultured

Table 1. Callus induction from anthers of six rice crosses cultured on modified N6 medium. Ludhiana, India.

Cross/parentage	Anthers cultured (no.)	Anthers forming calli (no.)	Callus induction (%)
Basmati 385/PR109	3,607	147	4.1
Pusa Basmati 1/PAU1198	4,899	522	10.7
Pusa Basmati 1/PR109	6,504	125	1.9
Basmati 370/IR64//Basmati 385	11,965	1,227	10.3
Basmati 385/IR64//Basmati 385	6,346	351	5.6
Basmati 385/PR4141//Basmati 385	8,822	564	6.4

Table 2. Plant regeneration from anther-derived calli in four rice crosses. Ludhiana, India.

Cross/parentage	Calli transferred to regeneration medium (no.)	Calli showing shoot differentiation (no.)	Calli regenerating green plants (%)	Green plants transferred to soil (no.)
Basmati 385/PR109	110	52 (47.3)	50.00	25
Pusa Basmati 1/PAU1198	103	44 (42.7)	47.36	14
Pusa Basmati 1/PR109	75	22 (27.3)	25.00	3
Basmati 370/IR64//Basmati 385	220	156 (70.1)	31.03	41

^aFigures in parentheses are percentage values.

on media based on N6 media composition:

- 2.5 mg 2,4-D L⁻¹ + 0.5 mg kinetin L⁻¹ + 3% sucrose.
- 2.5 mg 2,4-D L⁻¹ + 0.5 mg lunetin L⁻¹ + 5% sucrose.
- 2.5 mg 2,4-D L⁻¹ + 0.5 mg kinetin L⁻¹ + 3% maltose.
- 2.5 mg 2,4-D L⁻¹ + 0.5 mg kinetin L⁻¹ + 5% maltose.

Cultured anthers from all crosses exhibited callusing with varying frequency (1.9-10.7%). Highest callusing (10.7%) was observed in the cross Pusa Basmati 1 /PAU1198 on medium supplemented with 2.5 mg, 2,4-D L⁻¹ + 0.5 mg lunetin L⁻¹ + 3% maltose. N6 medium was found superior to Murashige and Skoog's, Blayde's, SK-8, and R-2 media for anther culture (Chu 1982, Lenka and Reddy 1994). Ammonium